

**PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS
AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN
VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART XVI.
PHOTOCHEMICAL REDUCTION OF CERIC TUNGSTATE
SOL BY GLUCOSE**

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Photochemical reduction of ceric tungstate sol by glucose has been investigated in dark and in light. Ceric content of the sol has been estimated.

The experimental arrangement is the same as discussed in Part I of this series (*J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 500).

Preparation of the Sol.—An unstable colloidal solution of ceric tungstate is obtained when 0.5 g. of sodium tungstate, dissolved in 100 c.c. of distilled water are added while sbaking to 100 c. c. of 6% aq. solution of ceric ammonium nitrate. This sol coagulated on standing for some time. On dialysis with distilled water (ρ_{H} near about 6), the coagulation is rather accelerated. But when dialysis is carried out with the help of a very dilute solution of HNO_3 (ρ_{H} 4) colloidal ceric tungstate, which remains stable for several days, is formed. The stability is due to a small amount of adsorbed ceric salt. And if this stabilising ceric salt is removed by adding a reducing agent, such as glucose or laevulose, which instantaneously reduces ceric salt in the dark, the sol coagulates immediately. Hence it is unsuitable for investigations on photochemical reactions especially photochemical reductions.

The stabilising ceric ion can, however, be replaced by a polyvalent cation which is not easily reduced by glucose, laevulose etc. Thorium nitrate was chosen for the purpose. To 20 litres of distilled water is added 3 g. of thorium nitrate and the ρ_{H} is kept near about 4 by adding nitric acid. This constitutes the dialysing liquid. When the ceric tungstate sol prepared as usual, is dialysed with the above liquid, thorium ion gradually replaces stabilising ceric ion. When glucose is added to this dialysed sol, it no longer coagulates. This sol increases in viscosity very slowly and can be kept stable for months.

By a similar method ceric molybdate, vanadate etc. may be prepared and the process may be extended for the preparation of other complex ceric sols.

In this paper, we have studied the photochemical reduction of ceric tungstate by glucose.

The ceric content of the sol was estimated iodometrically. The results obtained were further checked by titration with the ferrous ammonium sulphate (*cf.* Part VII).

Here also by passing pure nitrogen through the reaction mixture for a sufficiently long time, the induction period is much reduced and the photo-stationary state eliminated. No dark reaction was found between ceric tungstate and glucose for 6 hours. The light reaction was studied for 2 hours in all.

The velocity of reaction is given by $dx/dt = k(a-x)^{0.5}$ i.e. the velocity constant $k = 2/t \left\{ \frac{1}{a-x} - \frac{1}{a} \right\}$ (1)

TABLE I

Effect of varying the time.

Conc. of ceric tungstate (i.e. ceric equivalent) = 0.0168M. I_{abs} in ergs/cm²/sec = 1350
 Conc. of glucose = 5%. p_H 4.1.

Time after induction period.	Thiosulphate (0.0025M) for 0.25 c.c. reaction mixture.	$k \times 10^4$	Quantum efficiency.
0 min	1.42 c.c.		
6	1.20	3.65	
120	1.05	3.84	2.0
		Mean. 3.50	

TABLE II

Effect of varying the reductant conc.

Temp. = 25°. I_{abs} in ergs/cm²/sec. = 1350. Conc. of sol = 0.0168 M. p_H = 4.1

Conc. of glucose	$k_1 \times 10^4$
10%	3.78
5	3.50
2.5	3.65

Under otherwise identical conditions, in presence of excess of reductant the velocity of reaction is independent of the concentration of reductant.

TABLE III

Effect of varying the concentration of sol.

Temp. = 25°. I_{abs} in ergs/cm²/sec. = 1350
 p_H = 4.1, Conc. of glucose = 2.5%

Conc. of sol.	$k_1 \times 10^4$
0.0169M	3.68
0.0276	3.76

TABLE IV

Effect of varying the intensity of light absorbed.

Temp. = 25°. Conc. of sol = 0.016M. Conc. of glucose = 2.5%. p_H = 4.1.

I_{abs} in ergs/cm ² /sec.	$k_1 \times 10^4$
1350	3.68
697	2.80

From Table III it is evident that velocity of reaction is independent of the concentration of the sol. From Table IV it appears that the velocity of reaction varies as the square root of the intensity of absorbed radiation.

Temperature Coefficient of the Reaction.—The temperature coefficient $k_{25}^{\circ}/k_{15}^{\circ}$ of the photoreduction is of the order of 1.1–1.3.

Quantum yield of the Photo-process.—The quantum efficiency of the process was of the order of 2.

TABLE V
Effect of polarised light.

Conc. of sol = 0.0168M. Temp. = 25°. $\mu_H = 4.1$. Conc. of
Glucose = 2.5%.

Nature of light in which the reaction was carried out.	I_{abs} in ergs/cm ² /sec.	$k_1 \times 10^4$	k_1 for 150 ergs./cm ² /sec.
Unpolarised	1350	3.85	1.22
l-Circularly polarised	150	1.25	
d-Circularly polarised	150	0.80	

From Table V it is noticed that $V_0 = V_L = V_D$ the terms having the usual significance.

The mechanism of reaction is similar to that with ceric borate (Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 102).

$$dx/dt = k_2 I_{abs} (a - x)^{3/2} = C_B$$

$$\text{Now } C_B = k' C_B / k' + k' C_B$$

where C_B is the surface concentration of glucose and C_B , its bulk concentration.

When the reductant (glucose) is in excess, $k' + k C_B$ becomes practically equal to $k' C_B$ and the reaction becomes independent of the concentration of reductant under otherwise identical conditions. And this has been experimentally found to be the case.

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